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USE OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE PREPARATION OF FUTURE DENTISTS

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ЗАСТОСУВАННЯ ПЕДАГОГІЧНИХ ТЕХНОЛОГІЙ ПРИ ПІДГОТОВЦІ МАЙБУТНІХ СТОМАТОЛОГІВ

Abstract.

At the current stage of health care development, more and more attention is paid to patient safety, ethical issues, increasing the responsibility of health professionals, a high level of professional skills and the rapid evolution of procedures and methods. The above requires the adaptation of a study program and the use of all available educational tools and technologies in the training of future medical professionals. The aim of the study was to conduct a theoretical analysis of scientific psychological and pedagogical, methodological and medical publications, methodological work of the department on the use of pedagogical technologies in the training of future dentists. The use of modern pedagogical technologies, in particular stimulation learning technologies and case technologies, in the process of professional training of future dentists performs several important functions: control, as it reveals the knowledge, skills and abilities of students; educational, because it requires students to achieve a certain level of education; educational, as is the formation of personal qualities of future doctors. By effectively organizing independent and classroom activities of the student, the teacher promotes development of clinical thinking, which inevitably becomes the basis for qualified and successful doctor's formation. Simulation training and case technologies contribute to the formation of professional competence of future professionals, skills and abilities of their mental activity, personality development, ability for self-studying, changing the paradigm of thinking, the ability to process large amounts of information, as well as the development of quality requirements for a specialist who must respond adequately and professionally in different situations, to be systematic and effective.

Simulation learning technologies allow you to repeatedly and accurately reproduce important clinical scenarios and provide an opportunity to adapt the learning situation for each student.

Анотація.

На сучасному етапі розвитку сфери охорони здоров'я все більше уваги приділяється безпеці пацієнтів, етичним питанням, збільшенню відповідальності медичних працівників, високому рівню необхідної професійної кваліфікації та швидкій еволюції процедур та методів. Вищезазначене вимагає адаптування навчальних програм та використання усіх наявних освітніх інструментів і технологій при професійній підготовці майбутніх медичних фахівців. Метою дослідження було провести теоретичний аналіз наукових психолого-педагогічних, методичних та медичних публікацій, методичної роботи кафедри щодо застосування педагогічних технологій в процесі професійної підготовки майбутніх стоматологів. Використання сучасних педагогічних технологій, зокрема технологій стимуляційного навчання та кейс-технології, в процесі професійної підготовки майбутніх стоматологів виконує кілька важливих функцій: контролюючу, оскільки виявляє знання, уміння та навички студентів; навчальну, тому що вимагає досягнення студентами певного рівня навчання; виховну, оскільки відбувається формування особистісних якостей майбутніх лікарів. Ефективно організовуючи самостійну й аудиторну діяльність студента, викладач сприяє розвитку клінічного мислення, що неодмінно стає основою формування кваліфікованих та успішних лікарів. Симуляційне навчання та кейс-технології сприяють формуванню професійної компетентності майбутніх фахівців, вмінь та навичок їхньої розумової діяльності, розвитку особистості, здатності до самонавчання, зміні парадигми мислення, вмінню переробляти значні об'єми інформації; а також розвитку вимог щодо якості фахівця, який повинен адекватно та професійно реагувати в різних ситуаціях, відрізнятися системністю та ефективністю дій. Технології симуляційного навчання дозволяють багаторазово та точно відтворити важливі клінічні сценарії та надають можливість адаптувати навчальну ситуацію для кожного студента.

Keywords: *pedagogical technologies, training, teacher, student, dentistry.*

Ключові слова: *педагогічні технології, навчання, викладач, студент, стоматологія.*

Introduction. At the current stage of health care development, more and more attention is paid to patient safety, ethical issues, increasing the responsibility of health professionals, a high level of professional skills and the rapid evolution of procedures and methods [1-3]. The above requires the adaptation of a study program and the use of all available educational tools and technologies in the training of future medical professionals. The aim of the study was to conduct a theoretical analysis of scientific psychological and pedagogical, methodological and medical publications, methodological work of the department on the use of pedagogical technologies in the training of future dentists [4].

Materials and methods of the study. Analysis of psychological and pedagogical, methodical literature, materials of educational and methodical conferences, methodical work of the department. Theoretical methods (analysis, synthesis, generalization, comparison, systematization, pedagogical modeling, theoretical forecasting) were used to achieve the goal and clarify the nature and features of the use of modern pedagogical technologies in the educational process.

Results obtained. The rapid decrease in the price of computing power and the elemental base of computers, the sharp growth of the market of mobile devices and applications contribute to the mass spread of virtual reality technologies and make it possible to sharply reduce the costs of educational materials. The use of virtual reality in the practice of professional training of future dentists radically transforms the principle of visual content of education, and fully corresponds to the global trend in teaching disciplines, which consists in supplementing traditional approaches with modern methods of information transmission: expanding the

availability of electronic libraries, anatomical databases, the appearance of perfect simulators, which model the structures of the human body according to the system and topographic principle with the possibility of building planar projections and three-dimensional three-dimensional body models. The virtual identity of real objects, their universality and multifunctionality can give the future doctor greater life experience in perception, in the implementation of actions. The high efficiency of implementation, the use of virtual reality as a full-fledged educational equipment that competes with traditional approaches, requires the presence of educational programs that have a script, a rigid algorithm of actions, which allows them to act as an educational technology. In their absence, only the teacher can transmit knowledge to the student. As a way of transferring and learning knowledge, the existing means of virtual reality make high demands on the teaching staff, whose active and competent position will allow the introduction of new technologies. The introduction of virtual reality tools expands the boundaries of the principles of visibility and accessibility. At the same time, the insufficient development of specialized content and the lack of established educational technologies can cause difficulties in the widespread implementation of these educational tools by teachers. Anticipatory work in this segment is combined with the creation of specialized educational programs for the professional training of teachers and should become an actual direction for the implementation of virtual reality technologies in the practice of teaching medical disciplines.

In order to form future doctors' clinical thinking in the educational process, case-study technologies are implemented in parallel with the improvement of traditional ones. The case method, or the method of situa-

tional exercises, is a teaching method that makes it possible to bring the learning process closer to the real practical activities of specialists. It promotes the development of ingenuity, the ability to solve problems, develops the ability to analyze and diagnose problems. This pedagogical tool helps to deepen the understanding of the topic, develop imagination, practically test the theory, explore ideas, identify patterns, relationships, formulate hypotheses, increase motivation, encourage thinking and discussion, get additional information, deepen knowledge, confirm views, apply analytical thinking, ability to solve problems and draw rational conclusions, develop communication skills, combine theoretical knowledge with practical problem solving, turn abstract knowledge into skills and abilities. In the field of medical pedagogy, this technique allows developing clinical thinking based on the principles of evidence-based medicine, improving practical skills. This method is successfully used all over the world in teaching medical sciences. This pedagogical technology can be implemented in different ways. It can be a format of work in small groups, a business role-playing method, a discussion method, standardized patients, etc. [5]. However, one of the important ways of implementing the case study methodology is the use of information and educational web technologies, which makes the learning process interactive, effective and allows scaling educational materials to a large audience at the same time. With the help of information and educational web technologies, opportunities for a wider range of clinical cases, including rather rare ones, for qualitative visualization of additional research methods are revealed, which is impossible with the traditional training format. Access to interactive clinical cases is open and implemented using Internet access. An important advantage of the case method of learning is that this experience can be repeated if necessary and mastered according to an individual learning trajectory at a convenient pace with the help of Internet access. Interactive cases are widely presented on the websites of some medical educational institutions and in the Internet versions of medical journals, world societies of doctors of various specialties. Cases are illustrated materials that are shown to the user in a certain sequence. The user receives information about the patient using videos, graphic images, diagrams, etc., and after some time gets the opportunity to choose one or another action, assume a diagnosis, carry out a differential diagnosis, prescribe an examination, treatment. An interesting foreign project is the Open Labyrinth system, where the case method of learning is implemented using a special platform for creating and reviewing cases. In Ukraine, the study of the medical discipline using the case method began recently and needs to be developed and implemented in the practice of training modern specialists. Case technology is a complex and effective tool of innovative learning technology, which at the same time not only reflects a practical problem, but also actualizes a certain set of knowledge that must be mastered for its solution, and also successfully combines educational, analytical and educational activities, which increases effectiveness of modern educational tasks [6, 7]. The essence of case technology

is that students are offered a real clinical situation, the description of which simultaneously reflects not only any practical problem, but also actualizes a certain set of knowledge that must be mastered in order to understand a specific task. Until now, there is no certain standard for presenting cases from medical disciplines [8]. Usually, cases are presented in printed form or on electronic media, multimedia presentations, photos, diagrams, tables are included in the text, which makes them more visual for students. Case technology is an active problem-situational analysis based on learning by solving specific problems – situations (cases) – by a group of students. With joint efforts, it is necessary to analyze the symptoms, possible causes of its occurrence, find a practical solution, evaluate the proposed solutions and choose the most optimal one. Cases for independent work are more extensive and contain more information [9]. The use of case technology during the study of the academic discipline «Dentistry» helps students better remember complex topics, develop and train clinical thinking, master the skills of differential diagnosis of various pathologies, clearly and succinctly formulate their thoughts; develops the ability to listen, thereby stimulating interest in education. The organization of the educational process of professional training of future doctors with the use of cases makes it possible to prepare specialists as much as possible for taking the «KROK» exam.

Conclusions. The use of modern pedagogical technologies, in particular stimulation learning technologies and case technologies, in the process of professional training of future dentists performs several important functions: control, as it reveals the knowledge, skills and abilities of students; educational, because it requires students to achieve a certain level of education; educational, as is the formation of personal qualities of future doctors. By effectively organizing independent and classroom activities of the student, the teacher promotes development of clinical thinking, which inevitably becomes the basis for qualified and successful doctor's formation. Simulation training and case technologies contribute to the formation of professional competence of future professionals, skills and abilities of their mental activity, personality development, ability for self-studying, changing the paradigm of thinking, the ability to process large amounts of information, as well as the development of quality requirements for a specialist who must respond adequately and professionally in different situations, to be systematic and effective. Simulation learning technologies allow you to repeatedly and accurately reproduce important clinical scenarios and provide an opportunity to adapt the learning situation for each student.

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